

1 **Appendix S1: Technical details and supplemental figures and tables**

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3 Title: Rapid enhancement of multiple ecosystem services following the restoration of a coastal
4 foundation species

5 Running Head: Restoration enhances ecosystem services

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7 Journal: Ecological Applications

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Species Density					
Fish or Invert	Habitat	Resampled Mean	Std. Dev. (~SEM)	95% CI	Habitat Diff.
Fish	UNVEG	1.51	0.09	(1.32, 1.68)	a
Fish	2016	1.91	0.13	(1.65, 2.15)	b
Fish	2015	1.88	0.15	(1.61, 2.16)	b
Fish	REF	1.82	0.09	(1.65, 1.98)	b
Invert	UNVEG	1.49	0.12	(1.24, 1.72)	a
Invert	2016	1.63	0.13	(1.37, 1.87)	ab
Invert	2015	1.85	0.14	(1.58, 2.12)	bc
Invert	REF	2.16	0.13	(1.90, 2.43)	c

CPUE					
Fish or Invert	Habitat	Resampled Mean	Std. Dev. (~SEM)	95% CI	Habitat Diff.
Fish	UNVEG	6.41	0.89	(4.79, 8.17)	a
Fish	2016	7.80	1.10	(5.92, 10.22)	a
Fish	2015	8.56	1.33	(6.09, 11.35)	a
Fish	REF	14.21	1.71	(11.10, 17.69)	b
Invert	UNVEG	2.13	0.28	(1.58, 2.73)	a
Invert	2016	2.39	0.34	(1.78, 3.10)	a
Invert	2015	2.51	0.40	(1.85, 3.45)	a
Invert	REF	2.71	0.21	(2.30, 3.09)	a

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14 **Table S1. Macrofaunal Diversity (richness and abundance).** (Top) Species density for fish
15 and invertebrates and (Bottom) fish and invertebrate CPUE. Reported data include the resampled
16 mean and standard deviation (approximately equal to standard error), the 95% CI, and significant
17 differences ($p < 0.05$) between habitats, denoted by different letters. Each of the four habitat types
18 are shown in the order that they are plotted in the main text (“UNVEG”=Unvegetated,
19 “2016”=2016 Restoration, “2015”=2015 Restoration, and “REF”=Reference).

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25 **Figure S1.** Seagrass Time Series from 1931 to 2018 showing seagrass aerial extent in Elkhorn
26 Slough, CA starting at 26.01 hectares in 1931 to 15.62 in 2018. By the 1960s seagrass extent
27 dropped as low as ~3 hectares. These data are based on aerial imagery data. See Appendix 1:
28 Methods for details.

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40 **Figure S2.** Schematic of restoration design (2015 and 2016). Restoration plots were ~7 m away
 41 and reference beds were at least 25 m from restored plots at the time of transplanting. Illustration
 42 by Kathryn Beheshti.

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54 **Figure S3.** *Zostera marina* morphology and showing where shoots and rhizomes were trimmed
55 for transplanting (shoot, 20 cm; rhizome, 10 cm) and later lab processing (rhizome, 7 cm).

56 Illustration by Kathryn Beheshti.

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66 **Figure S4.** Expansion of reported structural attributes of restored (2015 and 2016) and reference
67 plots from August 2018 monitoring. Canopy height (cm) (per 0.25 cm²) for August 2018
68 monitoring effort for 2015 and 2016 restoration plots and reference bed plots. Presented canopy
69 height data is based on raw data. Different letters denote significant differences ($p < 0.05$)
70 between habitats.

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A.

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81 **Figure S5.** Shoot and rhizome mean biomass and epiphytic algae/diatom load by A) habitat type

82 and B) strata. Plotted is the biomass data (least square mean estimate \pm standard error) from

83 August 2018, 2 and 3 years post-transplantation for the 2015 and 2016 restorations. ANOVA p-

84 values are reported in the lower right (A) and upper left (B) hand corners. See Appendix 1:

85 Methods for details.

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94 **Figure S6.** Species accumulation curve for all trapped species across all trapping years (2016,
 95 2017, and 2018). The vertical dotted line represents where the lowest number of observations
 96 were, and therefore the comparison should be relative to the truncated value of 33 observations.

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109 **Figure S7.** Most commonly trapped species of invertebrates (left) and fishes (right) organized by

110 functional group. Photo credit: (1) Kat Beheshti, (2) Michael Langhans, (3) National Geographic,

111 (4) Monterey Bay Aquarium.

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Grazer Count

Species	Habitat	Resampled Mean	Std. Dev. (~SEM)	95% CI	Habitat Diff.
<i>Pentidotea resecata</i>	2016	4.43	1.26	(2.13, 7.21)	a
<i>Pentidotea resecata</i>	2015	4.86	1.25	(2.50, 7.32)	a
<i>Pentidotea resecata</i>	REF	0.81	0.34	(0.20, 1.50)	b
<i>Phyllaplysia taylori</i>	2016	3.01	0.81	(1.53, 4.74)	a
<i>Phyllaplysia taylori</i>	2015	2.92	1.00	(1.09, 5.23)	a
<i>Phyllaplysia taylori</i>	REF	1.93	0.58	(1.00, 3.10)	a

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Grazer Biomass

Species	Habitat	Resampled Mean	Std. Dev. (~SEM)	95% CI	Habitat Diff.
<i>Pentidotea resecata</i>	2016	0.03	0.005	(0.02, 0.04)	a
<i>Pentidotea resecata</i>	2015	0.03	0.007	(0.01, 0.04)	a
<i>Pentidotea resecata</i>	REF	0.005	0.003	(0.0004, 0.01)	b
<i>Phyllaplysia taylori</i>	2016	0.02	0.005	(0.01, 0.03)	a
<i>Phyllaplysia taylori</i>	2015	0.02	0.006	(0.007, 0.03)	a
<i>Phyllaplysia taylori</i>	REF	0.02	0.006	(0.01, 0.04)	a

124 **Figure S8.** Resampled means for A) counts and B) biomass (g, dry weight) of epifaunal grazers
125 *Pentidotea resecata* and *Phyllaplysia taylori* by habitat type. The data presented is from the
126 August 2018 monitoring effort. Different letters signify significant differences between habitat
127 types (“2015” = 2015 restoration, “2016” = 2016 restoration and “REF” = reference plots).
128 Count data are plotted as the bootstrap means (of resampling distribution) \pm standard deviation
129 (of the resampling distribution), which is approximately equal to SEM. We have also included
130 tables associated with each of the graphs that show the Mean, Std Dev (\sim SEM), 95% CI, and
131 significant habitat differences ($p < 0.05$).

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149 **Figure S9.** Organic carbon stocks (OC, kg/m³) by habitat and strata, plotted as the Least Square
 150 Means Estimate ± SEM. Different letters denote significant differences between habitats
 151 according to Tukey's HSD post-hoc tests. Unvegetated plots are in brown, restored plots in red,
 152 and reference plots in green. Stratum A (nearest to mouth of estuary) is characteristically sandy
 153 while stratum C is silty.

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 162 **Figure S10.** Average multifunctionality (\pm SEM) broken down by function. Top row is
 163 biogeochemical functions and the bottom row is biological functions. The y-axis is kept the same
 164 across functions to compare the relative contributions relative to the (best) 95th quantile (5th
 165 quantile for water temperature).

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177 **Methods: Appendix S1**

178 Seagrass time series

179 We developed a time series using geospatial data to quantify how much new seagrass habitat in
180 Elkhorn Slough was due to restoration plot expansion versus reference beds filling in and
181 expanding. Specific datasets were included (or excluded) for digitization based on the clarity of
182 the water at each seagrass site. It's possible that deeper portions of the beds closer to the channel
183 thalweg were under-represented in our delineations due to limited visibility. However, the good
184 consistency in the outline of the seagrass beds within each dataset group improved our
185 confidence in the delineations. The data presented in the seagrass time series reported as Figure
186 S1 was collected using similar aerial imagery extending as far back as 1931.

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188 Tracking structural attributes and mesograzer abundance as a proxy for restoration survival and
189 growth

190 In addition to measuring in situ canopy height, vegetative and flowering shoot density, we
191 harvested shoots from both restored and reference plots for later lab processing of shoot,
192 rhizome, and epiphyte biomass. We also collected data on the abundance and biomass of critical
193 mesograzers, *Phyllaplysia taylori* and *Pentidotea resecata* from harvested shoots. While other
194 invertebrate taxa were counted and recorded, we are only reporting on these two species because
195 of their well-characterized role in promoting the health of seagrass beds and because they made
196 up the majority of the mesograzer biomass across both restored and reference plots. Prior to
197 measuring the structural attributes of harvested shoots, all invertebrates were cleared from the
198 shoots themselves and the mesh bags they were held in.

199 To process each ramet, we first used a 3.8 cm single edge razor blade to scrape epiphytic algae
200 and diatom films off of the blades and wiped them on pre-weighed labeled cotton rounds before
201 placing them in the dehydrating oven for 72 hrs. Dry weight (g) was measured by subtracting the
202 weight of the clean, pre-weighed cotton round from the dried cotton round with sample. Once the
203 shoots were free of epiphytes we measured shoot lengths. Five representative shoot lengths were
204 measured from the tip of each blade to the base of the meristem at the first (most recent) node.
205 After shoot lengths were recorded we used the razor blade to cut the shoot from the rhizome at
206 the most recent note. We cut each rhizome to 7 cm in length and separately wrapped each shoot
207 and rhizome (n=50) in labeled pre-weighed foil. We poked tiny holes to allow the moisture to
208 escape and placed the samples in the dehydrating oven for 72 hrs for biomass in dry weight (g).
209 We then measured the dry weight of the sample by subtracting the pre-weighed foil weights from
210 the dried sample.

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212 Biodiversity of macrofauna

213 To quantify biodiversity of mobile macrofauna, a baited shrimp pot and a mid-water minnow
214 trap was deployed in each of the habitat types. To secure the trap arrays to their desired locations
215 and prevent them from shifting due to tidal currents, 2-4 plate weights (1.0-3.0 kg) were placed
216 in the corners of the shrimp pots to prevent them from sliding along the seafloor and Danforth
217 anchors were secured with line to the shrimp pots to further secure the trap arrays to their desired
218 location. Bait (frozen anchovies or sardines) was placed in a tennis ball can with holes drilled in
219 the base and top of the canister inside the shrimp pots. Depending on the size of the bait fish, the
220 canisters held between 5-8 fish. Travel-toothbrush holders with holes drilled on either side

221 served as bait containers for minnow traps and held 1 frozen fish. Mid-water minnow traps were
222 secured to the buoy line allowing enough slack to be suspended in the water column.

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224 Organic carbon stocks

225 Sediment cores were collected from October 2018-February 2020. All cores were immediately
226 stored in a refrigerator and processed within a week. First each core was sub-sampled into 2 cm
227 intervals and placed in a beaker to measure wet weight. Each interval was rinsed with DI water
228 and the sediment allowed to settle over 24 hours, after which we carefully poured off the surface
229 water and decanted the remaining water so as to prevent sediment loss. Each interval was rinsed
230 2-3 times (2 times for sandy sediment and 3 times for more silty sediment). Following the last
231 salt rinse, samples were dried and the dry weight (minus salts) was recorded. Each interval was
232 cone and quartered (Lewis and McConchie 1994) into two 10g subsamples ($\pm 0.1000\text{g}$), one for
233 TOM analyses and the other for grain size analysis (not reported). In order to remove inorganic
234 carbonates from the TOM subsamples, 1.2 Molar HCl was used to dissolve carbonates for 15
235 minutes. Afterwards, DI water was added and the sample sat for over 4 hours or until the
236 sediment settled. The diluted acid was decanted and DI water was added again. This process of
237 diluting the acid was repeated four times. After the final DI rinse the sediment was dried and dry
238 weight recorded. Acid washed sediment was then subsampled using cone and quartering
239 methods ($1.3 \pm 0.1000\text{g}$) and placed in crucibles to burn in the muffle furnace for loss-on-
240 ignition, LOI (Davies 1974). The muffle furnace was set to 550°C and samples burned for 3
241 hours. After samples cooled, crucibles were re-weighed and the difference between pre and post
242 combustion (LOI) is the TOM that was lost. To translate TOM to organic carbon (OC), we used
243 a power model ($y=0.22x^{1.1}$) derived using regional core data (Ward 2020). Carbon storage was

244 calculated by multiplying % OC and the bulk density of each interval, reported as kg OC m⁻³.

245 We used an ANOVA to determine differences in organic carbon stocks across habitats.

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247 **References: Appendix S1**

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